

Interview Reference Material

Protocol 2: Adoption & Implementation Evaluation

DPP Interoperability Platform — Practitioner Interview

*This handout accompanies the second part of the interview (Adoption & Implementation).
You may annotate it freely or refer back to it at any time during our discussion.*

Quick Reference: Key Abbreviations

DPP = Digital Product Passport **SoC** = Substances of Concern (REACH/RoHS) **LCA-EF** = Life Cycle Assessment / Environmental Footprint **JSON-LD** = JSON for Linked Data (W3C standard)
SPARQL = query language for knowledge graphs **OWL** = Web Ontology Language (vocabulary definitions) **PROV-O** = W3C Provenance Ontology

1 Requirements for Validation

Why We Present These Requirements

The platform was designed to satisfy **29 requirements** extracted from DPP standards, EU regulations, and initiative technical artifacts. **Protocol 1** covered schema design, extensions, mappings, linked data, provenance, and coverage requirements (19 requirements). **Protocol 2** covers the remaining **10 requirements** related to identifier resolution, API contracts, evaluation, and security.

Your task: review whether these requirements are **correct**, **complete**, and **appropriately prioritized**. Feel free to annotate the table.

1.1 Identifier Resolution (ID-01 – ID-05)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
ID-01	Heterogeneous identifier input	Resolver accepts 7 ID types: UUID, GTIN, VIN, serial, MPN, DID, LGTIN; scheme auto-detection	
ID-02	Resolution evidence & provenance	Evidence chain with source, match type, confidence score per candidate	
ID-03	Candidate ranking & scoring	Candidates ranked by confidence; top candidate selected for resolution	
ID-04	Identifier scheme mapping rules	Scheme-specific parsing via PREFIX_RULES, regex detection, normalization transforms	

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
ID-05	UPI granularity & uniqueness	Supports item-level (serial), batch-level (LGTIN), and model-level (GTIN) resolution	

1.2 API & Integration (API-01 – API-02)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
API-01	OpenAPI contracts	OpenAPI 3.0.3 spec for <code>/resolve</code> , <code>/normalize</code> , <code>/health</code> endpoints	
API-02	Example payloads & round-trip tests	7 test payloads (happy/minimal/partial-gaps); 512 automated tests	

1.3 Evaluation & Metrics (EV-01)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
EV-01	Labeled identifier set	Evaluation dataset with known-good identifier→passport mappings for precision/recall testing	

1.4 Security & Risk (SEC-01 – SEC-02)

ID	Requirement	Implementation Summary	Your Note
SEC-01	Threat-informed requirements	Documented threat model: spoofing, tampering, enumeration, denial-of-service	
SEC-02	Anti-abuse rules	Rate-limiting placeholders; non-sequential UUIDs; production hardening documented	

Validation Prompt

1. Are any of these requirements **unnecessary** or **incorrectly scoped**?
2. Are there **missing requirements** critical for DPP interoperability (e.g., access control, data sovereignty, versioning)?
3. Which requirements would you **prioritize differently** for a pilot deployment?

2 Platform Architecture

The platform consists of three components deployed as independent services:

3 Deployment and Access

Live Platform URLs

All components are deployed and publicly accessible:

Component	URL	Platform
Web Interface	https://dpp-interoperability-ui.vercel.app	Vercel
Microservices API	https://dpp-interoperability-microservices.onrender.com	Render.com
SPARQL Endpoint	https://api.dpp.triplydb.com/datasets/jorge-chumpitaz/Jorge-Testing/sparql	TriplyDB
Source Code	https://github.com/JorgeRenatoLeon/Thesis-Project	GitHub

Repository	Purpose	Language
Thesis-Project	Schema, mappings, OpenAPI specs, thesis	LaTeX, YAML
DPP-Interoperability-Microservices	Resolver + Normalizer services	TypeScript
DPP-Interoperability-UI	Web client interface	TypeScript/Next.js

4 Identifier Resolution Service

The resolver accepts any of **7 identifier types** and returns the canonical passport ID with confidence scores and evidence:

Type	Example	Standard
UUID	550e8400-e29b-41d4-a716-446655440000	RFC 4122
GTIN	04012345678901	GS1 (8/12/13/14-digit)
VIN	WVWZZZ3CZWE123456	ISO 3779
Serial	SER-2024-NMC-00142	Manufacturer-assigned
MPN	MPN-NMC811-PRO	Manufacturer part number
DID	did:web:cellco.example.com:dpp:bat001	W3C Decentralized ID
LGTIN	urn:epc:id:lgtin:4012345.012345.L0T01	GS1 lot-level GTIN

Table 5: Supported identifier types with examples

Resolver output example (abbreviated)

```

{
  "input": "04012345678901",
  "detected_type": "GTIN",
  "candidates": [
    {
      "passportId": "urn:uuid:550e8400-e29b-...",
      "confidence": 0.95,
      "evidence": [
        {
          "source": "internal-registry",
          "matchType": "exact",
          "confidence": 0.95
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}

```

5 DPP Normalizer Service

The normalizer transforms initiative-specific payloads into the Shared Core Schema using an **adapter pattern**:

Adapter	Initiative	Format	LOC	Extensions Mapped
TractusXAdapterJSON	Tractus-X	JSON	532	Battery + SoC
TractusXAdapterJSONLD	Tractus-X	JSON-LD	223	Battery + SoC (+ PROV-O)
BatteryPassAdapterJSON	Battery Pass	JSON	576	Battery + SoC + LCA-EF
BatteryPassAdapterJSONLD	Battery Pass	JSON-LD	194	Battery + SoC + LCA-EF (+ PROV-O)

Table 6: Adapter variants and configuration

5.1 Adding a New Adapter

To integrate a new DPP initiative, a developer implements one adapter module (~200–400 LOC):

1. Define field mappings from the initiative's schema to the Shared Core
2. Select which extensions the initiative supports
3. Implement `parse`, `map`, `validate`, and `report_gaps` methods

4. Register the adapter in the normalizer routing table
5. Write tests (typically 20–60 test cases)

No modifications to the core schema or other adapters are needed.

6 Dual Output Format

Every normalization produces two output formats from the same adapter pipeline:

Aspect	JSON Output	JSON-LD Output
Use case	REST APIs, application data	Semantic web, knowledge graphs
Linked Data	No	Yes (JSON-LD 1.1, W3C Rec 2020)
Provenance	provenance object	Same + provenanceLinkedData (PROV-O)
Context	None	@context array (core + extension contexts)
Identifier	passportId	@id (globally unique URI)
Type	productType	@type (OWL class reference)

7 SPARQL and Knowledge Graph

TriplyDB Knowledge Graph

The platform hosts a knowledge graph with 7 Digital Product Passports (~900 RDF triples) from two initiatives, queryable via SPARQL.

7.1 Dataset Contents

Passport	Initiative	Chemistry	Manufacturer
NMC-811-PRO	Tractus-X	NMC811	CellCo GmbH
LFP-MEGA-100	Tractus-X	LFP	NordBatt AB
LFP-IND-500	Battery Pass	LFP	VoltWerk GmbH
ESS-MEGA-2000	Battery Pass	NMC622	EnergieVerte S.A.
NMC532-Compact-EV	Tractus-X	NMC532	CellCo GmbH
LTO-Cycle-Max	Battery Pass	LTO	Toshiba
SmartSensor-IoT-v3	Battery Pass	—	PhilipSense (electronics)

7.2 Example SPARQL Query

Cross-initiative carbon footprint comparison

```

PREFIX dpp: <https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/core#>
PREFIX battery: <https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/battery#>
PREFIX lcaef: <https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/vocab/lca-ef#>

SELECT ?manufacturer ?model ?chemistry ?co2total
WHERE {
  GRAPH ?g {
    ?passport a dpp:DigitalProductPassport ;
              dpp:manufacturer ?mfr ;
              dpp:extensions ?ext .
    ?mfr dpp:legalName ?manufacturer .
  }
}

```

```

    ?passport dpp:model ?model .
    ?ext dpp:battery ?bat .
    ?bat battery:chemistry ?chem .
    ?chem battery:chemistryType ?chemistry .
    ?ext dpp:lcaEf ?lca .
    ?lca lcaef:carbonFootprint ?cf .
    ?cf lcaef:total ?co2total .
  }
}
ORDER BY ?co2total

```

8 Live Demonstration Guide

Demonstration Sequence

During the live demonstration, you will see the following five capabilities in action. Feel free to request specific scenarios or identifiers at any point.

1. Identifier Resolution

- Resolve a GTIN (e.g., 04012345678901) to a passport URI
- Resolve a VIN (e.g., WVWZZZ3CZWE123456) to a passport URI
- Resolve a DID (e.g., did:web:cellco.example.com:dpp:bat001)
- Observe confidence scores and evidence chain

2. DPP Normalization (JSON)

- Normalize a Tractus-X battery payload (JSON format)
- View the DPP Preview Card rendering (visual summary)
- Inspect core fields, battery extension (6 sub-objects), SoC extension
- Check provenance tab for per-field tracking

3. DPP Normalization (JSON-LD)

- Normalize a Battery Pass payload (JSON-LD format)
- Compare: same core schema, different extensions (Battery + SoC + LCA-EF)
- View `provenanceLinkedData` with PROV-O representation

4. Extension Composition

- Tractus-X profile: core + battery + SoC (no LCA-EF)
- Battery Pass profile: core + battery + SoC + LCA-EF (carbon footprint data)
- Gap report differences between profiles

5. SPARQL Explorer

- Run a cross-initiative query on the TriplyDB knowledge graph
- View results in table format and force-directed graph visualization
- Query across all 7 passports, all 5 chemistry types

9 Evaluation Metrics Summary

Metric	Description	Value
Automated test suite	Vitest (TypeScript)	512 tests (100%)
Test files	Across both repos	22 files
Identifier types supported	UUID, GTIN, VIN, Serial, MPN, DID, LGTIN	7 types
Adapter variants	Tractus-X + Battery Pass (JSON + JSON-LD)	4 adapters
Extension modules	Battery, SoC, LCA-EF, Food	4 modules
Core fields	Product-agnostic	17 fields
Domain fields	Across all extensions	~60 fields
OWL vocabularies	Hosted at jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/	5 modules
TriplyDB passports	Cross-initiative knowledge graph	7 DPPs
RDF triples	In TriplyDB dataset	~900
SPARQL lines saved	vs. REST API for cross-initiative analytics	5.4× fewer
Deployment	Vercel + Render.com + TriplyDB	3 services
Docker Compose	Single-command local deployment	Available

Table 7: Platform evaluation metrics

10 Adapter Pattern: Extensibility

A key claim of the platform is that adding a new DPP initiative requires only one adapter module without modifying the core:

Step	What It Involves
1. Define mappings	Map initiative field paths to core/extension field paths (CSV file)
2. Implement adapter	TypeScript module: <code>parse()</code> , <code>map()</code> , <code>validate()</code> , <code>reportGaps()</code>
3. Select extensions	Declare which extension modules the initiative supports
4. Create OWL vocab	If new domain fields needed: new ontology + JSON-LD context
5. Write tests	Unit + integration tests (typically 20–60 tests per adapter)
6. Register adapter	Add to normalizer routing table (one line of code)

Current mapping statistics:

- Tractus-X to Core: 43 field mappings (CSV)
- Battery Pass to Core: 45 field mappings (CSV)

11 Discussion Questions Reference

For your reference, these are the main topics we will discuss during Protocol 2. You do not need to prepare answers in advance—we will walk through them together.

- C1.** In your experience, what are the biggest barriers to exchanging DPP data across organizations or initiatives today?
- C2.** Is linked data / JSON-LD adoption realistic in your context? Would having dual output (JSON for apps + JSON-LD for knowledge graphs) ease the transition?
- C3.** Does the adapter pattern (Section 5) address your integration concerns? What would be hardest about adding your initiative?
- D1.** Based on the live demonstration, does the implementation match your expectations? What surprised you?

- D2.** Is dual output (JSON + JSON-LD) sufficient, or would you need additional formats (e.g., CSV, XML, XBRL)?
- D3.** How does your organization currently identify its products? Could those identifiers work with this resolver?
- E1.** What acceptance criteria would make this platform viable for a pilot deployment in your organization?
- E2.** Are there requirements for real-world DPP interoperability that we may have overlooked?
- E3.** If we prioritized the next three improvements, what would you recommend?

12 Open-Source and Reproducibility

Aspect	Detail
License	Open-source (GitHub)
Deployment	Docker Compose single-command: <code>docker compose up</code>
Test reproducibility	<code>npx vitest run</code> (512 tests, 100% pass rate)
Schema source of truth	Primary repo: <code>schema/</code> and <code>openapi/</code> directories
Vocabulary persistence	https://jorgerenatoleon.github.io/DPP-Interoperability-Microservices/ (future: <code>w3id.org/dpp-interop/</code> redirect planned)
CI pipeline	GitHub Actions: lint + build + test on Node.js 20/22

— End of Protocol 2 Handout —